

Financial Analysis of Hydropower Project Development in Nepal using FINPLAN Approach

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Keywords

Hydropower, shareholders' return, Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC), Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE), financial ratio,

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Executive Summary

A 100 MW Hydropower Plant is planned for development an investment cost of \$100 million (NPR 14,000 million). The financial analysis of the project is carried out using FINPLAN. The analysis of cash inflows and outflows of NGL scenario e. with no concession loan indicates a positive Net Present Value (NPV) (NPR 2,956 million) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR)of 12.8%, which is higher than the WACC of 8%, indicating the project's feasibility at a debt-equity ratio of 0.7. The project's NPV and IRR are sensitive to changes in electricity prices, generation capacity, and construction period. The analysis shows that the project remains profitable even up to a 20% reduction in electricity price below the tariff rate (NPR 6.6/kWh), indicating the tariff resilience of the project. The scenario analysis shows that even though there is no significant increment in IRR, the WACC decreased from 7.5% in the NGL scenario i.e. with no concession loan to 5.1% in the GL40_2.5% scenario, increasing the bankability of the project. Also, the LCOE decreased from NPR 5.87/kWh in the NGL scenario to 4.67 kWh in the GL40_2.5% scenario, i.e., with a high concession loan.

The results show that blended and concessional finance can substantially improve bankability by reducing WACC. The scenarios with lower interest rates and long-term loans yield higher IRR and positive NPV, implying the need of soft/concession loans available via export credit. Access to blended financing is thus crucial for project bankability and attracting long-term investment. At the same time, future financing frameworks need to account for climate resilience, given the vulnerability of seasonal hydropower generation to changing river flows and extreme weather events.

It is recommended that the Governments should look to increase the use of green bonds and concessional loans through export credits to help improve the IRR, increase the bankability of the project and overall feasibility of the project. In addition, a stable tariff framework need to be developed based on the affordability of the consumer and financial sustainability of the project

1. Introduction

Hydropower is the primary energy source in Nepal, accounting for 97% of the total electricity supply, while the remaining energy comes from solar and thermal sources (NEA, 2024). The total installed capacity of hydropower in Nepal is 3,200 MW, with a peak demand of 2,200 MW projected for 2024 (NEA, 2024). Due to the seasonal variability in hydroelectricity generation, Nepal experiences an energy deficit during the dry season and a surplus during the wet season. To balance its energy supply, Nepal imports electricity from neighboring India during the dry season and exports it to India and Bangladesh during the wet season. Nepal's Sixteenth Five-Year Plan (2081/82–2085/86) underscores the need for accelerated hydropower development to strengthen energy security and expand access (NPC, 2024). Complementing this, the Electricity Development Roadmap (MoEWRI, 2025) sets an ambitious target of 28,000 MW by 2035, indicating strong policy commitment and providing clear direction for investment and financing frameworks (MoEWRI, 2025).

While the development of hydropower plays a crucial role in Nepal's overall progress, its capital-intensive nature and long construction timelines mean that benefits are not realized as quickly as with solar and thermal power plants. The huge investments required for hydropower projects necessitate a detailed financial analysis. This includes feasibility studies, thorough planning, and engineering work before the project can begin generating power and revenue. Given the extensive work involved in hydropower development, it is vital to assess the economic and financial viability of the project to attract investors' capital. To evaluate financial instruments and provide shareholders with insights into the project's financial health, the FINPLAN approach is useful, offering information on NPV, IRR, debt-equity ratio, and other detailed financial analyses

2. Methodology

The financial analysis of the power project is carried out using the FINPLAN approach. The methodological flowchart is as shown in Figure 1. The FINPLAN is an Input-Output model, where the inputs are the assumptions such as the source of financing and investment plan, plant information like construction period, sales rate, and quantity, inflation rate, and taxation terms. Based on the input parameters, FINPLAN carries out a financial analysis. The case needs to be balanced with a standby facility and flow to the short-term deposit as low as possible so that the project has enough capital available to

operate without needing to deposit excess amounts in its short-term account. Once the case is balanced, the sensitivity analysis is carried out to observe the sensitivity of major input parameters in the financial health of the project. The scenario analysis is carried out in the FINPLAN by creating various investment cases.

Figure 1 Methodological Flowchart

- **Assumptions:**

The total investment costs for hydropower can vary significantly based on the site, design choices, and local labor and material costs. Due to the extensive civil works involved in hydropower projects, the costs of materials and labor are more significant compared to those of other renewable technologies.

A 100 MW hydropower plant is set to be developed in Sunadrijal, located 15 km northeast of the Kathmandu Valley. The investment required for this project is considered to be 100 million USD (IRENA, 2024). The Nepal Electricity Authority (NEA), which is the sole authority for electricity generation, transmission, and distribution in Nepal, has guaranteed a purchase price of NRs 6.4 per kWh for the power generated (NEA, 2024). The expected economic life of the plant is 40 years. Once operational, hydropower plants typically require minimal maintenance, leading to low operational costs. As a result, the annual operating and maintenance cost is projected to be 2.5% of the capital cost ((IRENA, 2024), with an annual escalation rate of 6% (MOF, 2025).

The depreciation rate for fixed assets is set at 15% using the declining balance method before switching to the linear method. Additionally, the annual insurance cost is 0.25% of the annualized capital cost. The price at which the NEA purchases power is expected to increase by 7% annually for the first five years, after which it will remain constant. The scenario analysis is carried out based on different investment plans as shown in Table 1. The first scenario (NGL) is when there is no concessional green loan; the project is financed by a project loan from financial institutions and shareholders' equity. In Nepal, the World Bank provides financing support through the International Development Association (IDA), offering concessional loans. As Nepal is graduating from least developed countries to developing countries, the green loan rate would increase from 0.75% to 2.5% as depicted in GL40_2.5% and GL40_0.75% scenarios.

Table 1: Assumptions for scenario analysis

Scenarios	Description
NGL	No green loan
GL40_2.5%	40% Green loan at 2.5%;
GL40_0.75%	40% Green Loan at 0.75% interest rate
GL60_2.5%	60% Green Loan at 2.5% interest rate

- **Sensitivity Analysis**

Investing in hydropower presents certain risks due to the high initial investment and long gestation period. To assess these risks, a financial feasibility analysis is essential, as it provides initial insights for launching the project. The sensitivity of the shareholders' return (NPV and IRR), under various input parameters for the NGL scenario, is considered as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters considered for sensitivity analysis

	% Change in capacity factor							
	-15%	-10%	-5%	0%	5%	10%		
Capacity factor (%)	38%	41%	43%	45%	47%	50%		
Construction period (Years)	4	5	6	7	8			
	% Change in Electricity price (NPR/kWh)							
	-30%	-20%	-15%	-10%	-5%	0%	5%	10%
Electricity price (NPR/kWh)	4.5	5.1	5.44	5.72	6.06	6.3	6.7	7.0

3. Results

The cash inflows and outflows related to construction and operational costs have been analyzed. During the construction period, cash flow increases significantly, as 75% of the investment capital is allocated to the first three years, during which most construction activities, such as civil and electromechanical works, take place. As the project approaches the commissioning phase, cash flow begins to decline. In this phase, debt and equity represent cash inflows, while capital investments and loan repayments are considered cash outflows.

Once the plant starts operations, cash outflows consist of operational and maintenance (O&M) costs, insurance costs, and interest payments, while cash inflows are generated from sales revenue. The analysis of cash inflows and outflows of NGL scenario indicates a positive NPV (NPR 2,956 million) and IRR of 12.8%, which is higher than the WACC of 8%, indicating the project's feasibility. During the construction period, the debt-to-equity ratio remains constant at 0.7. The LCOE is NPR 5.8/kWh, which indicates that the tariff rate or the Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) below this rate would not be profitable to the project.

Figure 2 Cash flow during project duration for NGL scenario

- **Scenario Analysis**

The scenario analysis was carried out under different investment plans as described in the assumptions of the methodology. A comparative analysis of all four scenarios was carried out for shareholders' return (Figure 3). The result shows that NPV and IRR is positive in all four scenarios. Since the green loan period is longer (40) years, there is no significant increase in IRR and NPV with the change in investment share and interest rate. It shows that if the credit length is longer the project yield positive NPV and IRR.

Figure 3 Scenario comparison for NPV and IRR

- **Sensitivity Analysis**

- **Effect of a change in electricity price**

The effect of a change in electricity price on NPV and IRR for NGL scenario is analysed. As the electricity price (PPA) rate changes between -30% to +10% (NPR 4.5-7.02 /kWh), the NPV and IRR also change. It shows that the project is feasible at the sales rate between NPR 4.5 and 5.1 per kWh against the base rate of NPR 6.33 per kWh. The highlighted figure shows the NPV and IRR's sensitivity with respect to the base value.

Figure 4 Sensitivity of electricity price in NPV and IRR

- **Effect of a change in the construction period**

The construction period is another important parameter that influences the overall profitability of the project. As the construction period elongates, there will be a delay in revenue generation, which will affect the overall cash flow of the project. So the NPV and IRR of the project are evaluated at different construction periods from 4 years to 9 years against the base year of 5 years; the NPV and IRR go on decreasing as the year increases as the revenue generation is delayed. The result shows that the project is feasible between the construction period of 8 and 9 years, as NPV is negative from year 9 onwards.

Figure 5 Sensitivity of construction period in NPV and IRR

- **Effect of a change in the capacity factor of the plant**

In Nepal, most hydropower plants are of the run-of-river type. During the wet season, these plants can operate at full capacity, while in the dry season, their generation is limited. As a result, the capacity factor of the plants varies significantly throughout the year. So the sensitivity analysis of the capacity factor is performed at -25% to +10%. The result shows that the project is still feasible at a 36% capacity factor.

Figure 6 Sensitivity of capacity factor in NPV and IRR

5. Discussion

The findings of this study show that the change in electricity price, construction period, and capacity factor of the plant can significantly vary the financial health of the project. Since these parameters are subject to change under different environments, the sensitivity of these parameters to the financial health was analysed. Considering the

seasonal variability of the hydropower, the electricity price can change. The profitability of the project is maintained even at a -20% reduction in the electricity price, maintaining the price between NPR 5.1-4.5 per unit. Similarly, the sensitivity of the construction period indicates that project is feasible with a delay in operation up to 3 years. In addition, the generation capacity, which also depends on the seasonal variability, makes the project beneficial to the investor between 34-36%. Whilst, the plant may be relatively robust against any one of these parameters, changes in several would further weaken the affordability of the project as a whole.

The scenario analysis from no green loan to up to 60% green loan suggests that a higher concession loan is attractive. The NPV increased from NPR 3 billion to NPR 4.6 billion, and the IRR also increased from 12.8% to 15%. Even though there is no significant increment in IRR, the WACC decreased from 7.5% in the NGL scenario to 5.1% in the GL40_2.5% scenario, increasing the bankability of the project. Also, the LCOE decreased from NPR 5.87/kWh in the NGL scenario to 4.67 kWh in the GL40_2.5% scenario, i.e., with a high concession loan. It thus highlights the need for blended financing with high concession in risky projects like hydropower.

The FINPLAN analysis highlights critical insights into the financial viability of hydropower projects, providing valuable guidance to both shareholders and financing institutions. As Nepal moves toward graduating from IDA concessional financing, the affordability of capital becomes more challenging, potentially requiring government intervention through sovereign-backed loans or targeted subsidies to keep tariffs competitive. At the same time, future financing frameworks need to account for climate resilience, given the vulnerability of seasonal hydropower generation to changing river flows and extreme weather events.

7. Conclusion

This study analysed the financial viability of a 100 MW hydropower plant development in Nepal. The project, financed through a blended and concessional structure at a 70:30 debt-to-equity ratio, yields IRR higher than WACC and a positive NPV. The project is viable at an average tariff of NPR 5.1/kWh compared to the base tariff of NPR 6.33/kWh. It also tolerates a three-year delay in commercial operation, enhancing investor confidence, and sustains viability at a 36% capacity factor against the base case of 45%. The results highlight the robustness of the project under different financing scenarios, underscoring its attractiveness for both equity holders and lending institutions. The scenarios with lower interest rates and long-term loans yield higher IRR and positive NPV, and is critical in lowering the WACC, implying the need of soft/concession loans available via export credit. The green bond and green credit financing are thus crucial for the feasibility of high-risk projects.

The financial viability of hydropower projects in Nepal depends not only on technical performance but also on sound financial structuring. A balance in tariff levels between

consumer affordability and financial sustainability is key for the project to remain both viable and socially acceptable. Access to blended financing is thus crucial for project bankability and attracting long-term investment. At the same time, a robust financial model that diversifies debt sources reduces market and financing risks, creating greater resilience under uncertain conditions.

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